

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

DETERMINE THE OCCURRENCE OF DOMAIN PARAMETERS OF HEARTRATE VARIABILITY IN MEDICAL STUDENTS AND EFFECT OF PSYCHOLOGICAL STRESS ON TIME

Dr Bilawal Wazir¹, Dr Babar Zia Sahi², Dr Ayesha Younus³

¹Services Institute of Medical Sciences, Lahore, ²Lahore Medical and Dental College, Lahore,
³Fatima Jinnah Medical University, Lahore.

Article Received: October 2020

Accepted: November 2020

Published: December 2020

Abstract:

***Objective:** The purpose of our study was to determine the occurrence of domain parameters of heartrate variability in medical students and effect of psychological stress on time.*

***Study design:** A cross sectional study.*

***Place and duration:** This study was conducted at the department of Physiology, Services Hospital Lahore for the duration of one year starting from August, 2019 to September, 2020.*

***Methodology:** In our present study 200 students were selected. We divide students into two groups on the basis of their depression anxiety stress scale questionnaire score, these two groups are stressed and stress free. Parameters of heart rate variability including frequency domain (low frequency (LF), high frequency (HF) and LF/HF ratio) and time domain (heart rate and Root Mean Square of the Successive Differences (RMSSD) of R-R intervals) of each participant were analyzed using lab chart 8 pro software and Electrocardiogram (ECG) of each participant were measured in lab room. SPSS v.20 was used for the analysis of data.*

***Results:** In our study Heart Rate Variability (HRV) is significantly reduce by stress. Between parameters of heartrate variability (HRV), Low Frequency (LF), LF/HF ratio were significantly raised in stress group (p-value <0.05) and high frequency (HF) parameter of HRV was significantly increased in stress free group (p-value <0.05).*

***Conclusion:** At the end of our study, we conclude that parameters of Heart rate variability are reflected as reduces cardiac parasympathetic nerve activity and stress upsurges cardiac sympathetic nerve activity. Biochemical parameters may be measured along with HRV for evaluating stress effects on cardiac autonomic function.*

***Keywords:** Stress, Heart Rate Variability, Depression Anxiety Stress Scale, Electrocardiogram, Medical Students*

Corresponding author:

Dr. Bilawal Wazir,

Services Institute of Medical Sciences, Lahore.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Bilawal Wazir et al, *Determine The Occurrence Of Domain Parameters Of Heartrate Variability In Medical Students And Effect Of Psychological Stress On Time.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Stress is a state of endangered homeostasis which disturbs numerous physiological processes in the body [1]. Medical education is considered stressful and remains an area of concern worldwide. Academic achievement in a competitive environment may produce drastic effects on young vulnerable medical students [2]. Unidentified and unattended esteem, cognitive functioning, academic achievement which can lead to deterioration in relationships and even dropout from medical school [3,4]. Brain takes an effective reaction to the stressful life events and initiates various central and peripheral physiological responses recognized as reactivity. Reactivity is associated with individual's emotions and behavior and leads to be activation of the various homeostatic regulatory systems like Hypothalamic Pituitary Adrenal axis and sympathoadrenal axis [5]. Perceived level of stress in an individual can be measured by using validated and reliable DASS (Depression Anxiety Stress Scale) questionnaire. On the basis of the score an individual can be labeled as stress free or suffering from mild, moderate, severe or extreme severe stress [6]. Stress results in an upsurge in sympathetic discharge and a decline in parasympathetic discharge enhance it disturbs the functioning of autonomic nervous system [7].

Autonomic nervous system responds towards various stressors by alternating arousal, breathing and heart rate [8]. Enhanced sympathetic activity affects various cardiovascular functions of the body including blood pressure, heart rate, ventricular depolarization and heart rate variability (HRV) [9]. Reduced parasympathetic activity of the body can be reflected by reduced cardiac vagal tone [10]. The capability of autonomic nervous system to deal with stressors depends upon high level of resting vagal tone [11]. Reduced meet situational demand and makes him more prone towards developing life threatening conditions including rhythm disturbances of heart [12]. Stress-induced sympathovagal imbalance can be investigated by analyzing HRV. Fluctuations in the activity of autonomic nervous system exert changes on heart rate and are reflected by HRV. The overall effect of sympathetic or parasympathetic nervous system on heart rate can be determined by calculating R-R intervals (RMSSD), a time domain component of HRV. Beat to beat frequency variations can be analyzed by spectral analysis of HRV in terms of high frequency (HF) and low frequency (LF) components [13].

High frequency component of HRV is regulated by vagal tone. Whereas changes in outflow of both vagal

and sympathetic tone is reflected by change in lower frequency component of HRV. The LF/HF ratio shows the balance among parasympathetic and sympathetic nervous system. Stress is accompanied by a decrease in HF component of heart rate variability and increase in activity reduction in parasympathetic activity [14]. In order to minimize skewness of distribution LF and HF components of HRV are measured in normalized units. Alternation in heart rate variability is an important indicator for cardiovascular mortality and morbidity. Since medical education is known for its stressful effects, this study is conducted to measure and compare the effect of stress on autonomic nervous system by determining time and frequency domain components of HRV in stressed and stress-free medical students.

METHODOLOGY:

This cross-sectional study was conducted at the department of Physiology, Services Hospital Lahore for the duration of one year starting from August, 2019 to September, 2020. 70 healthy students of Services Hospital Lahore from 1st and 2nd year MBBS with age of 18 to 25 years were included. At first, 21-item Depression Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS) proforma was distributed among 200 MBBS Students. Those who scored 19-25 on the proforma were categorized as moderate stress individuals while those who scored 0-14 on DASS proforma were categorized as stress-free. Individuals with any chronic ailment like hypertension diabetes or asthma were excluded from the study. Among the eligible students, 35 students were randomly selected in both groups through balloting method. Informed consent was taken from all the study participants and they were asked to visit the Power Lab Room of the department between 9.00 to 11.00 AM. They were instructed in advance to refrain from drinking tea or coffee. Once the participants arrived, they were asked to sit and relax for five minutes. Participants were instructed to remove any metallic items like keys, mobile phone, belt, etc. Measures were taken to avoid any noise distractions in the room. A ten minutes ECG was recorded by using power lab model Yam 4/25T in sitting posture. They were asked to avoid body movements during ECG recording.

Heart rate variability of the participants was analyzed from recorded ECG according to the guidelines published by North American Society of Pacing Electrophysiology. Low frequency component, High frequency component and the ratio of Low to High frequency components of HRV were measured by analyzing frequency domain parameter of HRV using fast Fourier transform (FFT) system. Time domain and Frequency domain parameters of HRV were measured

and compared among stressed and stress-free group. In time domain components Heart rate and Root Mean Square of the Successive Differences (RMSSD) of R-R intervals were measured while in frequency domain parameters LF, HF and LF/HF ratio were measured. All the variables of HRV were log transformed in order to avoid skewness of distribution. For the analysis of data, Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 was used. Significant statistical difference among two groups was assessed by the application of Independent sample test. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

RESULTS:

Depression Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS) proforma was distributed among 200 MBBS Students. Those who scored 19-25 on the proforma were categorized as moderate stress individuals while those who scored 0-14 on DASS proforma were categorized as stress-free. Among these students 72 (36%) returned the proforma so the response rate was 128 (64%). 86(43%) students scored in a range of 19-25 while 42 (21%) scored in a range of 0-14 (Table No 01).

Table No 01: Distribution of Participants According to DASS Proforma

	Scores	Qty	%age
Response	0-14 number	42	21%
	15-25 number	86	43%
No response	Not fill proforma	72	36%
Total	0-25	200	100%

Compares Time domain and Frequency domain parameters of HRV among stress and non-stress group. Heart rate was significantly raised in stressed group as compared to stress-free group. Whereas RMSSD of RR intervals was prolonged in stress-free group as compared to stress group. Among the Frequency domain parameters of HRV, high frequency component of HRV in terms of both absolute and normalized units was significantly reduced in stressed group, whereas low frequency component (normalized unit) of HRV & L F/HF ratio was markedly raised in stressed group.

Table No 02: Comparison of Time and Frequency Domain Parameters in Stress and Stress-Free Group

HRV parameters	Stress Group (Mean±S.D)	Stress free Group (Mean±S.D)	P-Value
Heart Rate Per Minute	79.74 ±4.51	74.73 ±5.17	0.000
RMSSD R-R interval	40.82± 12.79	46.94 ±15.42	0.075
LFms2	1048.20 ±347.60	883.80 ±423.41	0.080
HFms2	606.45 ±401.06	832.68 ±463.12	0.032
LF/HF	4.13 ±0.77	2.76 ±0.54	0.033
L F nu	92.66 ±4.27	89.36 ±4.54	0.017
H F nu	1.42 ±0.88	1.93 ±1.07	0.027

DISCUSSION:

Psychological stress disrupts student capabilities along with several physiological and psychological processes including functioning of autonomic nervous system. Heart rate variability is an important indicator which reflects the functioning of autonomic nervous system. Stress in medical students is an area of global concern. It affects psychological well-being of medical students and affects the functioning and effects of autonomic nervous system. Time and frequency domain parameters of HRV, reflects the activity of autonomic nervous system. Present study determines the effect of stress on time and frequency domain parameters of heart rate variability. In comparison with the stress-free individuals the stressed individuals showed an increase in heart rate, LF/HF ratio and LF parameter of HRV. Stressed individuals had a reduced RMSSD of R-R interval and HF component of HRV which shows that they have poor vagal activity as compared to the non-stressed individuals.

Montano and colleagues concluded that High Frequency component of HRV reflects the cardiac vagal nerve activity while Low Frequency component reflects the cardiac sympathetic nerve activity. LF/HF ratio acts as a weighing scale between cardiac sympathetic and parasympathetic nerve activity [15] Current study endorses the belief that stress upsurges the sympathetic nerve activity and decreases the parasympathetic nerve activity as reflected by an increased heart rate and a reduced HF component of HRV in stressed group. Findings of this study are in accordance with a previous study on a group of doctors who complained psychological stress at work. It was observed that in comparison with the stress-free subjects, the doctors had a reduced HF component of

HRV, making them susceptible for developing cardiac rhythm disturbances [16]. Current study also seconds the findings reported by Eller and group who conducted study on stressed engineers & teachers and found decreased HF component of HRV as compared to stress free individuals [17]. In contrast to previous studies, this study measured both time and frequency domain parameters of HRV and compares these parameters among stress and stress-free medical students.

Increase in LF/HF ratio of HRV reveals cardiac autonomic imbalance with a predominance of cardiac sympathetic nerve activity. Hintsanen and coworkers performed a study on office workers and concluded that psychological stress in office workers resulted in an increase in LF/HF ratio which is in line with the findings of our study [18]. Takada and colleagues showed that use of stress coping strategies increases HF component of HRV and decreases LF/HF ratio [19]. This shows that stress coping strategies increase the Cardiac vagal nerve activity and decreases the cardiac sympathetic nerve activity. Similar findings were reported by Mina kuchi and coworkers [20]. LF Component of HRV reflects the cardiac sympathetic nerve activity and its value is raised as a result of stress. Collins and group reported an increase in LF component of HRV in high strain group [21]. Kemp and associates also reported similar findings with difference that they conducted the study on depressed individuals [22].

CONCLUSION:

At the end of our study, we conclude that parameters of Heart rate variability are reflected as reduces cardiac parasympathetic nerve activity and stress upsurges cardiac sympathetic nerve activity.

Biochemical parameters may be measured along with HRV for evaluating stress effects on cardiac autonomic function.

REFERENCES:

1. Al-Sowaygh ZH. Academic distress, perceived stress and coping strategies among dental students in Saudi Arabia. *Saudi Dent J.* 2013; 25: 97-105.
2. Pinto VN, Wasnik S, Joshi SM, Velankar DH. Medical students' perceptions of stress factors affecting their academic performance, perceived stress and stress management techniques. *Int J Community Med Public Health.* 2018; 5: 191-6.
3. Talih F, Daher M, Daou D, Ajaltouni J. Examining burnout, depression, and attitudes regarding drug use among Lebanese medical students during the 4 years of medical school. *Acad Psychiatry.* 2018; 42: 288-96.
4. Heinen I, Bullinger M, Kocalevent RD. Perceived stress in first year medical students-associations with personal resources and emotional distress. *BMC Med Educ.* 2017; 7: 4-9.
5. Smeets T. Autonomic and hypothalamic pituitary adrenal stress resilience: impact of cardiac vagal tone. *Biol Psychol.* 2016; 84(2):290-5.
6. Lovibond PF, Lovibond SH. The structure of negative emotional states: Comparison of the Depression Anxiety Stress Scales (DASS) with the Beck Depression and Anxiety Inventories. *Behav Res Ther.* 2018; 33(3): 335-43.
7. Malik M, Bigger JT, Camm AJ, Kleiger RE, Malliani A, Moss AJ, et al. Heart rate variability: Standards of measurement, physiological interpretation, and clinical use. *Eur Heart J.* 2014; 17(3): 354-81.
8. Porges SW. The polyvagal perspective. *Biol Psychol.* 2007; 74(2): 116-43.
9. Lagraauw HM, Kuiper J, Bot I. Acute and chronic psychological stress as risk factors for cardiovascular disease: Insights gained from epidemiological, clinical and experimental studies. *Brain Behav Immun.* 2015; 50:18-30.
10. Park G, Thayer JF. From the heart to the mind: cardiac vagal tone modulates top-down and bottom-up visual perception and attention to emotional stimuli. *Front Psychol.* 2014; 5: 278-82
11. Wood SK, Valentino RJ. The brain norepinephrine system, stress and cardiovascular vulnerability. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev.* 2017; 74(Pt B): 393-400.
12. Scott BG, Weems C F. Resting vagal tone and vagal response to stress: associations with anxiety, aggression, and perceived anxiety control among youths. *Psychophysiology.* 2014; 51(8): 718-27.
13. Thayer JF, ÅhsF, Fredrikson M, Sollers JJ 3rd, Wager TD. A meta-analysis of heart rate variability and neuroimaging studies: implications for heart rate variability as a marker of stress and health. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev.* 2012; 36(2): 747-56.
14. Castaldo R, Melillo P, Bracale U, Caserta M, Triassi M, Pecchia L. Acute mental stress assessment via short term HRV analysis in healthy adults: A systematic review with meta-analysis. *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control.* 2015; 18: 370-77.
15. Montano N, Porta A, Cogliati C, Costantino G, Tobaldini E, Casali KR, et al. Heart rate variability explored in the frequency domain: a tool to investigate the link between heart and behavior. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev.* 2018; 33(2): 71-80.
16. Hernández-Gaytan SI, Rothenberg SJ, Landsbergis P, Becerril LC, León-León D, Collins SM, et al. Job strain and heart rate variability in resident physicians within a general hospital. *Am J Ind Med.* 2013; 56(1): 38-48.
17. Eller NH, Kristiansen J, Hansen AM. Long-term effects of psychosocial factors of home and work on biomarkers of stress. *Int J Psychophysiol.* 2012; 79(2): 195-202.
18. Hintsanen M, Elovainio M, Puttonen S, Kivimäki M, Koskinen T, Raitakari OT, et al. Effort reward imbalance, heart rate, and heart rate variability: The Cardiovascular Risk in Young Finns Study. *Int J Behav Med.* 2017; 14(14): 202-12.
19. Takada M, Ebara T, Kamijima M. Heart rate variability assessment in Japanese workers recovered from depressive disorders resulting from job stress: measurements in the workplace. *Int Arch Occup Environ Health.* 2014; 83(5): 521-9.
20. Minakuchi E, Ohnishi E, Ohnishi J, Sakamoto S, Hori M, Motomura M, et al. Evaluation of mental stress by physiological indices derived from finger plethysmography. *J Physiol Anthropol.* 2013; 32: 17.
21. Collins SM, Karasek RA, Costas K. Job strain and autonomic indices of cardiovascular disease risk. *American J Ind Med.* 2015; 48(3): 182-93.
22. Kemp AH, Quintana DS, Felmingham KL, Matthews S, Jelinek HF. Depression, comorbid anxiety disorders, and heart rate variability in physically healthy, unmedicated patients: implications for cardiovascular risk. *PLoS One.* 2012; 7(2): e30777.